

Infinite Product Representation for Central Binomial Coefficients

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Abstract

We introduce an elegant infinite product for central binomial coefficients.

Theorem 1. *If $n \in \mathbb{C} \setminus \{-1, -2, \dots\}$, then*

$$\binom{2n}{n} = \prod_{k=n+1}^{\infty} \frac{k^2}{k^2 - n^2},$$

where $\binom{2n}{n}$ denotes the central binomial coefficients.

Proof. Leonhard Euler gave the following infinite product of the factorial [1]:

$$n! = \prod_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\left(1 + \frac{1}{k}\right)^n}{1 + \frac{n}{k}}, \quad n \in \mathbb{C} \setminus \{-1, -2, \dots\}.$$

The definition of the binomial coefficient is given by:

$$\binom{l}{m} = \frac{l!}{m!(l-m)!}, \quad \text{for } l \geq m \geq 0.$$

Euler's infinite product definition for the factorial can be incorporated directly into the binomial coefficient, giving:

$$\binom{2n}{n} = \prod_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\left(1 + \frac{1}{k}\right)^{2n}}{1 + \frac{2n}{k}} \cdot \frac{\left(1 + \frac{n}{k}\right)^2}{\left(1 + \frac{1}{k}\right)^{2n}} = \prod_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(k+n)^2}{k(k+2n)} = \prod_{k=n+1}^{\infty} \frac{k^2}{k^2 - n^2}.$$

□

References

- [1] L. Euler, *Letter to Christian Goldbach dated October 13, 1729*, available at <http://www.math.dartmouth.edu/~euler/correspondence/letters/000715.pdf>.